

Innovative biomaterials
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devices

END-TO-END MULTIDISCIPLINARY OPTIMAL DESIGN FOR IMPROVED PERSONALIZED BIOACTIVE GLASS/CERAMIC BONE SUBSTITUTE IMPLANTS (ReBone): A NEW MSC PhD NETWORK

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INTRODUCTION

The musculoskeletal system is particularly susceptible to aging and traumatic occurrences and, thus, new solutions are required for patients who require bone-substitute implants to treat critical-size bone defects timely.

The **four-year ReBone Doctoral Network (2024-2027)**, funded by the Europe Horizon Marie Skłodowska Curie programme, aims to train a new generation of researchers working in this multidisciplinary field; specifically, **ten doctoral candidates** will jointly develop an innovative and integrated methodology to design and develop novel personalized ceramic-based bone substitute implants.

In order to achieve this ambitious purpose, a **European network of partners and associated partners** has been established encompassing diverse disciplines including materials engineering, biomechanics, clinics, mechano-biology, additive manufacturing technologies and mixed reality models for surgical planning simulations.

Clinical data will be used to create **personalized multi-scale models** of the implant at the organ level; concurrently, the design of device architecture, materials and parameters for the manufacturing technology will be optimized to achieve improved implant outcome in terms of optimal biomechanical performance related to the defect shape and anatomical location.

METHODS

Material technology

I – Development of high quality and reliable bioactive GC-based materials and related manufacturing technology

Bioengineering

II – Development of in-silico models for the prediction of the biomechanical properties of bone implants and of a multi-disciplinary optimization platform

Mechano-biology, clinics and mixed reality

III – Clinical perspective, mechano-biology and procedural planning in mixed reality space

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Define a procedure for clinical image analyses to inform the personalized bone-substitute design, fully validating it on four selected clinical cases;
- Pursue material formulations and related optimized printing processes based on Vat PhotoPolymerization (VPP) technology, characterised by high printing fidelity and minimal intrinsic material defects;
- Validate computational personalized models for predicting the biomechanical response of bone replacement implants made of glass-ceramics (GCs) or glass-ceramic/hydroxyapatite (GC/HA) and glass-ceramic/zirconia (GC/zirconia) composites;
- Validate algorithms for optimal design of implants with prescribed function and constraints;
- Devise a mixed reality surgical planning for the four selected clinical cases.

CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this contribution is to bring to the knowledge of the medical community, and in particular of the ESSKA, the engineering and technological solutions which are being developed within the ReBone consortium.

In the near future, during the development of the research program, further interactions are envisaged to contribute in closing the gap between the innovative engineering and technological solutions and the clinical practice.